

CALCULATION OF EFFICIENCY OF FLAT SOLAR COLLECTORS

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Abstract: The article examines the energy efficiency of the solar water heating collector. The operation procedure, elements and functions of the solar water heating collector are described. The methodology and expressions for calculating the energy efficiency of the solar water heating collector have been developed.

Keywords: solar water heating collector, energy efficiency, thermal energy, energy efficiency of solar collectors, solar hot water systems.

Introduction. The energy efficiency of solar collectors represents the ability to convert solar energy into thermal energy. Solar collectors often convert the sun directly into thermal energy, which offers somewhat lower energy costs and environmental benefits. To calculate and evaluate the energy efficiency of solar collectors, you can perform the following steps:

Solar collectors are used to heat industrial and household buildings, supply hot water for production processes and household needs. The most production processes that use hot and hot water ($30\div 90^{\circ}\text{C}$) together with domestic needs occur in the food and textile industries, so we focus on the use of solar collectors, its efficiency and resource saving. needed.

The solar collector is the main element of solar hot water systems [1-5].

Solar collectors are solar energy devices designed to absorb solar radiation and convert it into thermal energy [6-9].

The efficiency of the heat and hot water supply system largely depends on the efficiency of the solar collector. All structural features of any solar collectors should allow maximum absorption of solar energy and minimum heat loss. The more the collector system absorbs solar energy, the faster it converts this radiation into heat energy, and the less heat is lost on the way to the heat accumulator and the pipe to the consumer, the more efficiently this system works [10-12].

Materials and methods. A solar water heater (SWH) is a system designed to capture solar energy and convert it into thermal energy for heating water. This renewable energy technology can significantly reduce energy bills and environmental impact compared to conventional water heating methods. Here's

a comprehensive guide on how solar water heaters work, their components, benefits, and considerations.

Solar water heaters use solar energy to heat water through a collector. The basic operation involves:

1. Solar Collectors:

- Flat-Plate Collectors: These are commonly used in residential applications. They consist of a flat-plate absorber with a transparent cover to trap sunlight and a heat-absorbing element.

- Evacuated Tube Collectors: These collectors have multiple glass tubes with a vacuum between them, which improves efficiency by reducing heat loss.

2. Heat Transfer:

- Direct Circulation Systems: Water circulates directly through the collectors and into the storage tank. Suitable for areas with moderate freezing risks.

- Indirect Circulation Systems: A heat-transfer fluid (like antifreeze) circulates through the collectors, transferring heat to the water in the storage tank through a heat exchanger. Ideal for areas with freezing temperatures.

3. Storage Tank:

- A well-insulated tank stores the heated water, ensuring it remains hot until needed.

4. Controls and Valves:

- Thermostatic Controls: Regulate water temperature and manage the operation of the system.

- Check Valves: Prevent backflow of water.

5. Pumps (for active systems):

- Circulation Pump: Moves water or heat-transfer fluid between the collector and the storage tank.

The housing of flat solar collectors uses thermal insulation, reflective coating of glass, solid wall, which ensures a long service life. They are simply and reliably installed flat and on the roof, installed anywhere on the roof and buildings [15-19].

The efficiency of the solar collector is the ratio of useful heat energy to the incoming solar energy. In addition to thermal losses, in some cases optical losses also occur in the device. The optical efficiency determines what percentage of the radiation through the transparent coating reaches the collector and is absorbed by the absorber.

Results. To evaluate the efficiency and design parameters of solar collectors for a solar water heating system, we can use the given formulas. These formulas help determine the collector efficiency, required collector area, and potential fuel savings from using solar energy. Here's a detailed explanation and calculation process for each formula:

As a first approach, the efficiency of solar collectors can be calculated using the following formula [8]:

$$\eta = \eta_0 - \frac{k\Delta T}{E}, \quad (1)$$

where, η is the calculated value of FIK, %; η_0 is the optical efficiency of the device under normal conditions, %, k_1 is a coefficient depending on the type of collector and thermal insulation, ΔT is the temperature difference of the working body and the ambient temperature, °C, E is insulation, W/m^2 .

The efficiency of modern solar collectors is expressed by the following formula [20-22]:

$$\eta = \eta_0 - k_1 \frac{\Delta T}{E_g} - k \frac{\Delta T^2}{E_g}, \quad (2)$$

E_g - amount of total solar radiation falling on the collector, W/m^2 .

For a certain amount of hot water, we can calculate the working area of the required solar collector using the following formula.

$$A = \frac{1,16G(t_{c.w.} - t_{h.w.})}{\eta \sum_i g_i}, \quad (3)$$

here, G - amount of water, kg; $t_{c.w.}$, $t_{h.w.}$ -temperatures of cold and hot water, °C; $\sum_i g_i$ - the amount of total solar radiation falling on the surface of 1 m^2 per day, Wh/m^2 ; η -energy efficiency solar collector.

It is also recommended to calculate the efficiency of solar collectors using the following formula:

$$\eta = 0,8c \left\{ \theta - \frac{9U[t_1 + t_2/2 - t_e]}{\eta \sum_i g_i} \right\}, \quad (4)$$

here, U is the loss coefficient, the passport characteristic of the solar collector, $W/m^2 \cdot K$; in the absence of passport data, 8 $W/m^2 \cdot K$ for single-glazed collectors and 5 $W/m^2 \cdot K$ for double-glazed collectors can be obtained; t_1 and t_2 are temperatures of the working body at the inlet and outlet of the solar collector, °C; t_e -ambient temperature, °C.

In case of uneven consumption of hot water by months in devices without accumulator tanks, the calculation of the working area of solar collectors should be carried out according to the value of daily consumption of hot water every month and should take the largest part of the obtained working areas. Hourly

productivity of solar collectors g_i , kg/m^2 is determined by the following 5 formulas [23]:

$$g_i = \frac{0,86U}{\ln \frac{t_{\text{maxi}} - t_1}{t_{\text{maxi}} - t_2}}, \quad (5)$$

The equilibrium temperature of each hour t_{maxi} is determined by the following formula

$$t_{\text{maxi}} = \frac{q_{\theta i}}{U + t_{ei}}, \quad (6)$$

$q_{\theta i}$ - absorbed solar radiation intensity, W/m^2 ; t_{ei} - ambient temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The calculation of saving fuel resources due to the use of solar energy should be carried out according to the following formula:

$$B = 0,0342 \frac{Q}{\eta_{\text{ch}}}, \quad (7)$$

where, Q is the total amount of heat Q , GDj/year , the amount of heat produced in the solar collector during the year; η_{ch} - Efficiency of the modified heat source.

Conclesuons. When developing methods for calculating the efficiency of solar collectors, take into account the meteorological characteristics of the area, the amount of solar radiation, geographical latitude and albedo, insolation, annual precipitation, ambient temperature, air humidity, absolute pressure, cloud density, air dust level and aerosol amounts is appropriate.

These calculations provide a comprehensive approach to designing and evaluating the performance of solar water heaters. Adjusting inputs and formulas based on specific system parameters and conditions will yield accurate and useful results.

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